

Manufacturing of clay roof tiles from Agricultural residues

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Abstract-In the present scenario of sustainable construction, the effective utilization of agricultural waste materials has become essential. This project focuses on the partial replacement of clay with agricultural residue ashes such as rice husk ash (RHA), sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA), and palm leaf ash (PLA) for the production of low-cost clay roofing tiles. These waste materials, which are abundantly available, possess favorable physical and pozzolanic properties that improve tile performance. The study investigates different replacement percentage of each ashes (3%, 6%, and 9%) and evaluates their effect on strength, durability, and thermal properties. Results indicate that partial replacement reduces tile weight, enhances insulation, and maintains adequate strength. The use of these materials not only reduces manufacturing cost but also promotes eco-friendly waste management. This approach contributes to sustainable construction by converting agricultural waste into valuable building materials

Keywords: Rice husk ash (RHA), Sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA), Palm leaf ash (PLA), Optimum mix, Clay roofing tiles, Tile properties, sustainable construction, agricultural waste

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the construction industry has increasingly focused on developing sustainable and eco-friendly building materials to reduce environmental impact and conserve natural resources. Clay roofing tiles are widely used due to their durability and thermal performance; however, excessive extraction of natural clay leads to resource depletion. At the same time, large quantities of agricultural residues such as rice husk, sugarcane bagasse, and palm leaves are generated, creating disposal issues. These residues, when converted into ash, possess properties such as low density, porous structure, and reactive silica, making them suitable as partial replacement materials. In this study, rice husk ash (RHA), sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA), and palm leaf ash (PLA) are individually incorporated into clay at 3%, 6%, and 9% replacement levels to produce roofing tiles.

Experimental investigations including specific gravity, fineness, Atterberg limits, mechanical and thermal properties are carried out to evaluate performance. Results indicate that replacement up to 6% provides acceptable strength, water absorption and improved thermal behavior, while higher percentages lead to increased porosity and reduced strength. The study identifies an optimum replacement level and demonstrates the feasibility of producing lightweight, cost-effective, and sustainable roofing tiles using agricultural residues

GENERAL

Energy consumption and material demand in the construction sector are increasing rapidly, especially in developing countries like India. Traditional materials such as clay and cement require significant natural resources and energy for production, leading to environmental degradation. Agricultural residues are generated in large quantities every year and pose disposal challenges. Instead of treating them as waste, these materials can be effectively utilized in construction applications. Their incorporation into building materials reduces environmental pollution and promotes sustainable development. Roofing tiles made from clay are widely used due to their strength and durability. However, replacing a portion of clay with agricultural residue ash can reduce weight, improve thermal properties, and lower production costs. This makes them suitable for affordable housing and environmentally friendly construction practices

2. MATERIALS

2.1 Clay

For this study, locally available clay soil was used as the base material for roofing tile production. A combination of classic clay and lean clay was used to obtain the required plasticity and strength. The clay was tested for its index properties such as specific gravity, Atterberg limits, and particle size distribution as per IS standards:

Physical Properties:

Sr.No.	Property	Value
1	Liquid Limit	37.50%
2	Plastic Limit	16.66%
3	Clay Fraction	95%
4	Silt fraction	5%
5	Sand Fraction	0%

Table 1 Physical properties of clay

2.2 Rice Husk Ash (RHA)

Rice husk ash was obtained by controlled burning of rice husk and sieved through a 90-micron sieve to obtain fine particles. It was used as a partial replacement of clay at 3%, 6%, and 9%. The ash predominantly consists of amorphous silica with high surface area, which enhances its interaction with the clay matrix. Due to its porous structure and low specific gravity, it reduces plasticity and contributes to improved thermal insulation properties. The physical properties of the rice husk ash are detailed in below Table.

Physical Properties:

Property	Value
Specific Gravity	2.20
Fineness %	8.8
Appearance	Fine Powder in Grey colour

Table 2: physical properties of Rice Husk Ash

2.3 Sugarcane bagasse Ash (SCBA)

Sugarcane bagasse ash was collected from local sources and sieved through a 90-micron sieve. It was used as a partial replacement material in clay at 3%, 6%, and 9%. SCBA contains significant silica content and exhibits pozzolanic characteristics that influence the consistency and bonding behavior of the clay mix. Its inclusion leads to reduction in plasticity and modifies the microstructure by increasing pore spaces. The physical properties of the Sugarcane bagasse ash are detailed in below Table

Physical Properties:

Property	Value
Specific Gravity	2.40
Fineness %	8.6
Appearance	Fine Powder in black colour

Table 3: physical properties of Sugarcane Bagasse Ash**2.4 Palm Leaf Ash (PLA)**

Palm leaf ash was produced by burning dried palm leaves and sieved through a 90-micron sieve. It was used as a partial replacement material in clay at 3%, 6%, and 9%. PLA is lightweight and highly porous in nature, which significantly reduces the density of the mix and enhances thermal insulation. However, excessive addition increases void ratio, leading to reduction in strength. The physical properties of the Palm leaf ash are detailed in below Table

Physical Properties:

Property	Value
Specific Gravity	1.83
Fineness %	8.40
Appearance	Fine Powder in grey colour

Table 4: physical properties of Palm Leaf Ash**2.5 Water**

The water used in this research was potable and fit for drinking, with a pH value ranging from 6.5 to 8. The laboratory's available tap water was used for both mixing and curing the concrete.

3. METHODOLOGY

Tile Testing Methodology

Tests

➤ Flexural Strength Test:

The flexural strength of roofing tiles was determined to evaluate their load-bearing capacity and resistance to bending. The test was conducted in accordance with IS 2690 (Part 1): 2023 – Methods of Tests for Burnt Clay Building Materials.

➤ Water Absorption Test:

Water absorption of tiles was measured to assess porosity and durability characteristics. The test was carried out as per IS 2690 (Part 1): 2023, which specifies procedures for determining water absorption of burnt clay products.

➤ Permeability Test:

The permeability test was conducted to evaluate the resistance of tiles to water penetration under specified conditions. The procedure was followed as per relevant provisions in IS 654:1992 (Clay Roofing Tiles Specification)..

➤ Thermal Performance Test:

Thermal properties of the tiles were evaluated to determine heat transfer characteristics and insulation performance based on general heat transfer principles. This test is essential for assessing the suitability of tiles in reducing indoor temperature variations in roofing applications.

Mixture Proportions

The clay mix was prepared by partially replacing clay with agricultural residue ashes at different percentages. Each ash was used individually (not combined) at replacement levels of 3%, 6%, and 9% by weight of clay. The materials were thoroughly mixed with the required quantity of water to obtain a homogeneous and workable mix suitable for moulding. of size 200*175*20mm

Flexural Strength

The flexural strength test is carried out to determine the bending strength of clay tiles and is also known as the modulus of rupture. It indicates the maximum stress developed in the tile at the time of failure and is important for evaluating the effect of ash addition on material strength. The test is conducted using a three-point bending setup where the tile is supported at two ends and loaded at the centre until failure.

The flexural strength is calculated using:

$$F = 3Pl / 2BD^2$$

Where:

F = Flexural strength (N/mm²),

P = Breaking load (N),

l = Span (mm),

B = Width (mm)

Fig 1. Flexural Strength Testing Machine Fig 2. Specimen after Testing

Water Absorption Test

The water absorption test is conducted to determine the amount of water absorbed by clay tiles under specified conditions. It indicates the porosity and durability of the tile material and helps evaluate the effect of ash addition on density and compactness. Lower water absorption generally signifies better quality and improved resistance to weathering. In this test, the tile is first dried in an oven at 100–110°C until constant weight and its dry weight (A) is recorded. The specimen is then immersed in water for 24 hours, surface dried, and weighed again to obtain the wet weight (B)

The percentage water absorption is calculated as:

$$\text{Water Absorption} = (B - A) / A$$

A = Dry weight of tile (g),

B = Wet weight after 24 hours immersion (g).

This test is used to compare the porosity and performance of different ash-mixed tile compositions

Fig3. Specimen soaked for 24 hrs Fig4. Specimen after soaking

Permeability Test

The permeability test is conducted to determine the water-tightness of clay tiles. In this test, the tile is fixed at the bottom of a trough, sealed along the edges, and water is maintained at a height of 5 cm for 6 hours. After the test, the underside of the tile is examined. The tile is satisfactory if no water seepage or dripping is observed. This test checks the permeability (water penetration resistance) of the tile. It indicates the ability of the tile to resist water flow through its pores and cracks, which is essential for durability and leak-proof roofing performance.

Fig5. Permeability Test set-up

Fig6. Specimen after testing

Thermal Insulation Test

This procedure describes the method for achieving and maintaining a constant surface temperature of 60–70 °C using an electric hot plate and Infrared (IR) thermometer during laboratory testing. The method ensures uniform heating conditions and accuracy of experimental results. It is suitable for small laboratory-scale thermal exposure tests..

Fig7. Thermal Insulation Tests

Table 5. Experiment Result

Ash Type	Percentage Mixed	Water Absorption (%)	Thermal Insulation (°C)	Permeability	Flexural Strength (N/mm ²)	Overall Behaviour
Standard Tile	--	11.38	32	No seepage	4.64	Very Good
RHA Mixed Tile	3%	11.18	30.8	No seepage	4.34	Very Good
	6%	17.63	30.2	Slight dampness	4.39	Good
	9%	18.55	29.8	Minor seepage	4.17	Moderate
SCBA Mixed Tile	3%	11.88	30.5	No seepage	4.29	Very Good
	6%	10.98	31.0	No seepage	4.52	Excellent
	9%	12.18	31.3	Slight dampness	4.09	Moderate
PLA Mixed Tile	3%	11.45	30.0	No seepage	3.96	Good
	6%	22.17	29.5	Slight dampness	4.17	Poor
	9%	18.92	29.0	Minseepage	2.74	Poor

Table 6 Optimum Percentage and Best Performing Ash

Test Parameter	Optimum Percentage	Best Performing Ash	Reason
Water Absorption	6%	SCBA	Lowest absorption
Thermal Insulation	9%	PLA	Lowest temperature
Permeability	6%	SCBA	No seepage
Flexural Strength	6%	SCBA	Highest strength

Table 7 Final Optimum Mix

Rank	Mix	Performance
1	6% SCBA + Clay	Excellent
2	3% RHA + Clay	Very Good
3	3% SCBA + Clay	Good

Fig 8. Optimum Mix graph

3. CONCLUSION

This study presents the development of low-cost clay roofing tiles through the partial replacement of clay with agricultural residue ashes such as rice husk ash (RHA), sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA), and palm leaf ash (PLA). The work emphasizes sustainable construction by utilizing waste materials and reducing dependence on natural clay resources. Material characterization, mix proportions, and performance evaluation were carried out to study the effect of these ashes on properties such as plasticity, density, strength, water absorption, permeability, and thermal behavior. The results indicate that incorporation of ashes reduces plasticity and density while improving thermal insulation characteristics.

The study further identifies that replacement up to 6% provides optimum performance in terms of strength and durability, whereas higher percentages lead to increased porosity and reduced strength. Cost analysis shows that the use of locally available agricultural residues significantly lowers production cost, making the tiles suitable for low-cost housing applications. Among the materials studied, sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) exhibited comparatively better performance due to its higher silica content and pozzolanic characteristics, which enhance particle bonding and improve the microstructure of the clay matrix. Overall, the research establishes that agricultural residue ashes can be effectively utilized to produce lightweight, economical, and environmentally sustainable roofing tiles

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